

Embargo Notice for Scientific Article

Title of the Article: The combination of oral quercetin supplementation and exercise prevents brain mitochondrial biogenesis

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Journal: Genes & Nutrition

Manuscript DOI: 10.1007/s12263-014-0420-8

Date: 6th of February, 2024

To Whom It May Concern,

This document serves as a formal notice that the scientific article titled “The combination of oral quercetin supplementation and exercise prevents brain mitochondrial biogenesis”, is currently under embargo.

The embargo is in place as per the terms and conditions of Genes & Nutrition and will last until further notice. During the embargo period, the article cannot be publicly shared or disseminated through any digital or print medium.

Thank you for your understanding and cooperation.

Sincerely,

Rafael A. Casuso